

agr! BRIDGES

**“Building bridges between consumers and producers
by supporting short food supply chains through a
systemic, holistic, multi-actor approach-based Toolbox”**

(Grant Agreement 101000788)

Coordination and Support Action

“Let’s meet!” Event Validation Report

Responsible Partner: VEGEPOLYS VALLEY

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"Let's meet!" Event Validation Report – France

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1. Introduction

The present report summarises the activities of VEGEPOLYS VALLEY for the organisation and validation of the Culinary event in Pays de la Loire, Angers, on the 01/04/2023, the 05/04/2023 and the 08/04/2023. This event is one of the four “Let’s meet!” event concepts designed in agroBRIDGES Task 3.4 for the local promotion of Short Food Supply Chains, locally produced food and involved market actors, namely (i) Producer Events, (ii) Culinary Events, (iii) Celebrate local heroes / SFSCs, and (iv) Open Days. The organisation, planning and implementation of the event was performed using the guidelines and templates designed by FBCD for each event concept to enable actors in the agri-food sector in replicating the events in their local agri-food ecosystems.

The present report outlines all steps taken for the design, planning and implementation of the regional event, as well as the outcomes and evaluation of the event by the participants and the organising agroBRIDGES partner, to produce suggestions for the improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool. The remainder of the report is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 2** – Describing the concept selection, design, organisation and implementation of the Culinary event in Pays de la Loire, Nantes.
- **Chapter 3** – Outlining the validation results for the events by participants and the value found in the “Let’s meet!” guidelines by the organising partners when creating and launching their event.
- **Chapter 4** – Concluding remarks for the event and suggestions for improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool.

2. “Let’s meet!” event organisation details

2.1 Concept selection and definition of activities (programme)

The “Culinary event” is the event selected by VEGEPOLYS VALLEY to connect consumers to fresh and local products. During the opening of the Vegetal Pop Up Store from VEGEPOLYS VALLEY, 3 culinary events have been organized. For all of these culinary events, a chef had to cook meals with seasonal products coming from local producers.

- 01/04/2023: “From vegetable to plate”, managed by Lucas POTHIER from 11 A.M to 12.30 A.M
- 05/04/2023: “Vegetable bites”, managed by Pascal FAVRE D’ANNE from 11 A.M to 12.30 A.M
- 08/04/2023: “Edible gardens”, managed by François Xavier BEE from 11 A.M to 12.30 A.M

For the organisation of those three culinary events, we worked with several partners:

- “My pop-up Store” for the design and organisation of the pop-up store taking into consideration the material and logistic needs for a culinary event.
- The catering for the inauguration of the pop-up store announcing the culinary event with influencers and journalists

The creation of this pop-up store dedicated to local producers was a good opportunity to link with the culinary events. A lot of communication has been made about this shop and the event organized in the shop, including the culinary event. Moreover, the store was really well located, in a famous mall in Angers, where thousands of people came.

Table 1: Event programme

Title of activity	Short description	Date & Time (local)	Location
Inauguration	Presentation of the Pop Up Store : products, companies, partners, Agrobridges toolbox by VEGEPOLYS VALLEY, culinary events	31/03/2023	Atoll, in Angers
Culinary event 1	Presentation of the chef, the origin of the products, the recipe.	01/04/2023	Atoll, in Angers
Culinary event 2	Preparation of the dish.	05/04/2023	
Culinary event 3		08/04/2023	
	During the cooking time of the dish, the agroBRIDGES project was presented and the participants were invited to wait for the cooking in the reading area dedicated to agroBRIDGES tools.	11:00 – 12:30	
	Tasting of the finished cooked dish, around the central island		

2.2 Location, Venue/Space selection and arrangements

The Culinary event took place in the Pop-up Store dedicated to “Local Plant innovation”, located in the mall called Atoll in Angers. In the Pop-up Store, there was a place dedicated to:

- **the Culinary Event:** a corner in the pop-up store was organised as a kitchen
- **the agroBRIDGES Toolbox:** an island with different storey brought to light some agrobridges tools. A table and chairs were set up next to it to allow visitors to take time to discover the tools developed by the project. Two posters were printed to promote the Agrobridges’ project.

The place has been designed and set up by the provider “My Pop-up Store” in advance.

During the launching event, the cocktail has been booked with the caterer enable to propose local food.

Figure 1: Presentation of the place dedicated to agroBRIDGES (promotion of the project and toolbox)

Figure 2: Presentation of the place dedicated to the culinary event in the Pop Up Store

2.3 Personnel involved in the organisation of the event

For this event several persons have been requested.

Table 2: Estimated effort and expertise needed for the event

Specialisation	Number of employees	Expected role	In-house / External	Estimated effort (person days)
Communication time	1	Invitation and communication about the event, mobilization of journalists	In-house	
Printer	1	Print the tools, posters	In -house	0.25 person day

Catering	1	Food and drinks for guests	External	N/A
Global organisation	5	Rating scale, application file, promotion, communication	In-house	12 person days
Representation of VEGEPOLYS VALLEY	3	Present during the event	In-house	0.5 person day
Chef	3	Animation of the culinary events	External	2 person day
Influencers	3	Promotion and communication on social network	External	1 person day
Gastronomy Campus	1	Coordination of the culinary event	External	2 person day
My pop up store	4	Design the place	External	4 person day

2.3 Event material

The event graphic material used for this event are the following:

- Two posters made by the Communication Work Package Leaders and translated by VEGEPOLYS VALLEY.
- agroBRIDGES' logo hold in the store
- Guides and document printed about the tools developed by agroBRIDGES
- A tablet allowing to automatically pass the success stories in SFSC published in the tool "Yes you can".
- We had the "consent form" and the "satisfaction survey" with agroBRIDGES' logo.

Figure 3: Printed posters for the culinary event

2.4 Engagement of contributors and collaborators

The setting up of an ephemeral plant shop by VEGEPOLYS VALLEY has been planned since last year. In this Pop-Up Store are presented local products from different companies coming from the surrounding of Angers. That is why, it was a really good opportunity to organize, in the same time, in the shop an event related to agroBRIDGES. We decided quite fast to organize a culinary event with chefs cooking recipes with local products.

Vegepolys Valley has a partnership with the “campus de la gastronomie” (gastronomy campus) located in Angers. The “campus de la gastronomie” offers several training courses related to food and beverages. Through this, it was easy to mobilize reputable actors in the surrounding in their networks working on recipes based on local products.

The organisation of the culinary event in the pop-up store allows to take advantage of the communication made on the vegetal shop.

The chefs present to the event had to present their recipes, the origin of their product and promote agroBRIDGES (the objectives of the project and the tools developed).

Visitors had the option to leave their contact details in the store to be contacted later to be future ambassadors of agroBRIDGES Toolbox. They also had the opportunity with a suggestion box to leave their comments about the tools but also about “good ideas” and suggestions to develop new SFSC system (Hear My Voice tool).

The 3 chefs who participated to the culinary event had to complete a registration form.

2.5 Invitation of attendees and promotional activities implementation

To promote and communicate about the event, we established a big list of contacts:

- Start-ups and SMEs,
- producers,
- chambers of agriculture,
- associations and companies related to FSCS,
- inter-profession from different agricultural sectors
- public institutions
- cooperatives
- regional and local authorities

With this list of contacts representing more than 400, we sent an e-mail to announce the event (1 week before the first culinary event) and one recording before each culinary event (than means 30/03, 03/04 and 06/04). We also made publications on VEGEPOLYS VALLEY social networks (LinkedIn) and website. For the Pop-Up Store, we also have specific pages dedicated on Facebook, Instagram and another website. We made publications about agroBRIDGES.

With this communication and promotion about our Let's Meet event we knew that the sharing of the information and the world of mouth will work.

During the culinary event, influencers came to promote this event and talk about the agroBRIDGES tools highlighted in the store. Few posts mentioning @agroBRIDGES have been published on Instagram.

Figure 4: Publication dedicated to agroBRIDGES and the culinary events

The screenshot shows a website page for 'Le Végétal de Demain'. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links: ACCUEIL, ACTUALITÉS DU VÉGÉTAL, QUI SOMMES NOUS?, REJOINDRE LE VÉGÉTAL DE DEMAIN, and LA BOUTIQUE 2023. Below the menu, the page title is 'Le Végétal de Demain / La boutique 2023 / Les ateliers culinaires'. The main heading is 'Les ateliers culinaires'. Below this, there is a paragraph: 'Tout au long du mois d'avril, retrouvez-nous en boutique pour participer à des ateliers culinaires & thématiques ! Ces ateliers sont organisés dans le cadre du projet Européen AgroBridges, pour en savoir plus sur ce projet européens : cliquez sur son logo !'. The AgroBRIDGES logo is displayed below the text. Underneath, it says 'Atelier sur inscription, places limitées'. A list of events is provided: '1er Avril de 11h-12h30 avec LUCAS POTIER Chef à domicile / chef consultant « Du végétal à l'assiette », une Masterclasse pour appréhender de nouvelles recettes, échanger, et déguster !'. Two specific dishes are listed: '1er plat : Ravioles d'échalotes, bouillon d'oignons brûlés et d'algues wakomé, chapelure de pain' and '2ème plat : Quinoa au lait crémeux (façon riz au lait), poire fraîche, confiture de poire'. To the right of the text is a photograph of a chef in a white uniform and hat, looking down at a document.

levegetalddemain
L'ATOLL Angers-Beaucouzé (Page Officielle)

levegetalddemain Dans la cadre de la Boutique, le projet européen agroBRIDGES organise des Lab'Culinaire pour apprendre à cuisiner des produits #locaux, en partenariat avec le @campusdelagastronomie ! 🍴

Mercredi 5 Avril, le Chef étoilé Pascal FAVRE D'ANNE (@pascalfada) était présent pour animer un atelier intitulé "Bouchées Végétales" !

Au menu 🍴 :
🥗 Rouleau de printemps « tout végétal », céleri, pomme granny et vinaigrette truffes
🍷 Mousse persil, radis et champignons de Saumur

📅 Ne manquez pas les prochaines sessions ! Pour vous inscrire, rendez-vous sur <http://levegetalddemain.com> !

#végétal #végétalddemain #responsable #ateliers #cuisine #culinaires #ecoresponsable #beauté #naturels #produitsnaturels #bio #boutique #angers #food #chefsuisiniers #fleurs

Modifié · 3 j

campusdelagastronomie Merci @pascalfada d'avoir animé cet atelier pour le @campusdelagastronomie et @levegetalddemain 🙌🍴

3 i Répondre

14 J'aime
IL Y A 3 JOURS

Ajouter un commentaire... Publier

VEGEPOLYS VALLEY

7 083 abonnés
20 min · 🌐

📍 La Boutique éphémère 2023 est ouverte !
📅 du 1er au 29 avril 2023 📍 à l'Atoll à Angers (49)

Découvrez cet écran de produits innovants liés au végétal 🌱!

Vous souhaitez acheter en #circuitcourts ? Vous trouvez aussi dans cette boutique les outils et conseils du projet AgroBridges 📖 Le projet européen [AgroBridges Project 2021-2023](#) soutient la boutique du végétal, pour rendre disponible en #circuitcourt les innovations végétales au plus près du #consommateur

Profitez aussi de 📖 6 ateliers culinaires et 17 ateliers thématiques

✍️ <http://ow.ly/qLbn50NsRjz>

. Entrée boutique gratuite et ouverte à tous
. Ateliers sur inscription (attention places limitées - Pour les ateliers payants paiement par CB en ligne)

#levegetalddemain

3. Event implementation and outcomes

3.1 Event implementation

- For the 3 culinary workshops, the chef came 1 hour before the beginning of the event to prepare and install their material.
- For the 3 culinary workshops, there was a group of 6 to 8 persons registered and during the event, few visitors stayed with the group and assisted until the end.
- The participants were really interested, asking a lot of questions, taking notes.
- During the cooking time dedicated to the tools, a few people wanted to take printed tools with them.
- The intervention and preparation of the different chefs have been really interesting and tasty.

Figure 5: Pictures of the event

3.2 Event participation

Table 3: Event participation

Audience type	No. of participants
INAUGURATION of the pop-up store	
Producers	20
Caterer	2
Partners	22
Collaborators	10
Total	54
Culinary event 1	
Producers/ chef	2
Consumers	6
Partners	1
Collaborators	2
Total	11
Culinary event 2	
Producers/ chef	1

Audience type	No. of participants
Consumers	9
Media, journalists	1
Partners	1
Collaborators	1
Total	14
Culinary event 3	
Producers/ chef	1
Consumers	8
Media, journalists	3
Partners	1
Collaborators	2
Total	15

4. Event Validation

4.1.1 Validation of event concept by participants

Question	Yes		No		Not sure	
Were you familiar with the concept of Short Food Supply Chains before this event?	16		3		3	
Question	Absolutely agree	Agree	Do not agree or disagree	Disagree	Fully Disagree	No answer
Did you find this event informative about new/unknown types of food, preparation method of product coming from your region?	17	5	0	0	0	0
Did you find this event helpful for getting to know local food businesses, restaurants, their methods and efforts to bring local food closer to you?	16	6	0	0	0	0
Did you find the activities organised helpful to understand the value of local food, local recipes and their various benefits for your health, the environment, and the society?	4	14	0	3	1	0
Did you find enough information about how and where to find the local restaurants and kitchens and other hospitality businesses you've met?	11	9	1	1	0	0
Would you like another similar event to be organised in your region?	Every month or more	3-4 /year	Twice a year	Once a year	Never	No answer
	10	11	1	0	0	0

4.1.2 Validation of “Let’s meet!” guidelines and templates by the organising partner

Question #1: Did you find the event concepts relevant to your local agri-food ecosystem and organization?

The event was really relevant. It enables people to:

- learn how to cook good recipes, easily and not expensive with local products,
- use some local products,
- discover new products and where they can find them (in specific farm, farmers market)

Some professionals could come and make a professional appointment on site.

Question #2: Would you organize the same event again in your region? If yes, would you make any adjustments?

It could be interesting and relevant to organize the same event next year. However, to promote the agroBRIDGES tools, the explanation of the tools needs to be more accessible to the public (too long to read in a short time, organize B2B with the tools, etc.)

Question #3: Did you find the guidelines and templates sufficient for your event organization needs?

Yes.

Question #4: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines accurate enough to plan effectively?

Yes, without any problems.

Question #5: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines flexible enough to create an event tailored to your ecosystem/business needs?

Yes, totally.

4.1.3 Limitations and barriers of the organising partner

- **About the culinary event**

The main barrier was to find famous chefs available and agree to realize culinary events. Some of them didn't want to come because of the location, others because of the dates, the schedules. This event is a small project to mobilize big actors (if you want famous chef to come).

Moreover, it was not so easy to make agroBRIDGES tools understandable by the chef: they are used to talk about specific products and not technical tool. None of them knew about the project before the culinary workshops. They had to be introduced to the objectives of agroBRIDGES.

- **About the promotion and presentation of the tools**

The promotion of the agroBRIDGES tools was a bit complicated because it is not the final version of the tools, they are not yet online for the general public and the main page on the website is only translated in English.

In that kind of event, there is too much text in the different tools for somebody passing through the store.

4.1.4 Suggestions for improvement of the concept and guidelines

If we want to organize again that kind of event, we have to involve more the participants. We could organize a masterclass rather than a cooking class; something more participative.

Finally, we advise to organise the culinary event during a weekend and during a holiday period to have the maximum of participants.

5. Conclusions

This culinary event is very satisfying. The participants were happy and interested about the products, the recipes and the taste of the meals. Some people assisted to the 3 different culinary workshops.

It was a really good idea to organize this event in the global project of the pop-up store. With the open doors of the store in the street, the kitchen smells attracted a lot of people.

The "culinary event" organized as a one-time event would have been more difficult to have that amount of participant, communication and interest.